

From The Desk of Guest Editor....

Orthodontics At Cross Roads

Imagine a scenario, Lots of kiosks are opened in various shopping malls , markets and other prominent places of a city or a town. What is on offer? Are you having any orthodontic problem? Are your teeth malaligned? Are your jaws not properly placed? Do you want them corrected? Please get your mouth and face screened and scanned. You will get the report and your diagnosis. You will be asked to pay a certain amount through online payment, and the required appliance in the form of aligners will be printed and sent home to you with instructions. The Artificial intelligence with data algorithms and deep learning instructions to the sensors will be placed through robotic in the appliance system, which gets activated through some app in your mobile for the orthodontic movements to take place. A single aligner worn by the appliance will be activated, worn as per instructions and treatment rendered to the person Or an aligner fabricated with memory plastic (like a NiTi Wire).A computer analyst trained for the purpose will be doing the treatment, no requirement of an orthodontist or even a Dental Surgeon.

Is this fiction??This is indeed an extraordinary period in the orthodontic profession wherein the first speciality of Dentistry is converting into digital robots, treatment rendered and accomplished with greater efficiency, even if with suspect results. Establishing a proper diagnosis and treatment plan are essential to the success of overall treatment, but personal, physical and ethnic considerations are of paramount importance, especially in the field of Orthodontics. A meticulously developed treatment plan requires thorough analysis of multiple records (radiographs, photographs, digital models, scanning records) as well as general and local examination of the patient becomes important.

A comprehensive diagnosis derived from properly analyzed diagnostic records backed up with evidence based practice as well as long term data from outstanding clinicians/experts can reduce the risk of errors in the treatment being delivered.

Since 1900,when Edward H. Angle provided us with the edgewise appliance, the fixed orthodontic appliance has undergone many changes and modifications in form of Beggs appliance, Pre adjusted Edgewise appliances with conventional and self-ligatingbrackets. The philosophy of extraction versusnon- extraction orthodontic treatment under went a great debate and now, the curve is shifting towards Non Extraction Modality due to soft tissue facial concerns. Many visionaries like Dr Charles Tweed, Dr R M Ricketts , Dr Ronald Roth, Alan Brodie, Dr Mcnamara, Dr Alexander, to name a few, devoted their career to expanding the speciality to new dimensions. More treatment options offers an opportunity to decide whether to finish with brackets or aligners, use functional appliances, removable or fixed Herbst or Motion D appliance, Nickel Titanium wire or TMA, compliance have revolutionized the orthodontic practice.

But, Do you think that we will stay with conventional orthodontic practice or the market will force the orthodontist to practice according to their requirements. The companies have started to dictate terms to orthodontist to avail their services, whether using smart Technology or Invisalign, demand training specific to their system, benefiting the companies indirectly. Can an average Chess player even think of winning against a computer driven chess game. Can a normal orthodontist compete with company driven mechanized appliances, directly given to the patient, on demand, without the services of an orthodontist.

The last 2 decades have witnessed enormous changes in the practice of orthodontics. It started with Lingual Orthodontics, an esthetic option which appealed to teenagers or job oriented persons. Many courses were designed for the same. The emergence of temporary anchorage device increased the treatment options, even converting jaw surgeries to non surgical options in certain cases of skeletal discrepancy. The next decade gave way to fully digital workflow, imaging technology and the aligner treatment. This can be corroborated when we see the trend of scientific presentations tilting towards aligners from conventional mechano therapy.

To make the diagnostic process more accurate and more data available for treating cases with desirable and efficient orthodontic tooth movement, the use of artificial intelligence has grown significantly. The machine learning is able to learn through data, to solve the problems by itself, and the Algorithms used to predict outcomes facilitate the resolution of orthodontic problems through the appliances directly without human input.

Recent technological innovations used in the last decade with the introduction of Cone Beam Tomography, 3D photography, 2-3 D Cephalometrics, Morphometrics, intraoral scanners, 3-5 D Printers, development of softwares utilizing machine learning and now the conglomeration with Robotics and Mobile Apps, becoming more minute and precise will move the teeth with commands of both human and non human nature.

Orthodontics is a complex subject wherein, the facial and dental diagnosis may lead to extractions and proximal slicing of teeth or expansion of the arches with bone as such. The studies have shown that with the use of TADs and MARPE, along with the aligners, the roots of the teeth are not managed efficiently in relation to bone structure as shown by various CBCT studies. The surgical orthodontic cases, the cranio-facial anomalies, extraction modalities, orthodontic cases requiring specific root movements, skeletal disharmonies cannot be yet, handled appropriately as yet by aligners but research is undergoing to use AI which is trying to overcome these hurdles.

Dr Nikhilesh Vaid, President of World Federation of Orthodontics opined in Seminars of Orthodontics "The orthodontic landscape is metamorphosing itself and the infusion of newer biomaterials, inter-

specialty techniques and appliance systems warrants a structured and organized approach to orthodontic efficacy and efficiency." Ray Kurzweil, the famed American futurist has made some predictions that seemed improbable at the turn of the century. His predictions were based on the law of accelerating returns. The idea is that technology advances exponentially because every advance helps fuel the next one. Simply speaking, in the realm of computing, Moore's law has actually plotted exponential growth and nanotechnology is a reality today. Ray Kurzweil in his book "**The singularity is near**", states that computers will routinely pass the Turing test by 2029.

In the same decade, nanobots will be able to practically cure any disease and heal any wound. Nanobots will also spontaneously create food by reorganizing existing matter. He also predicts that by the 2030s, advancing technology will enable the understanding of the human brain workflow to such a degree that it will be possible to upload someone's neural structure into a robotic body. All predictions are open to interpretation, and technology might grow exponentially to a point where cognitive sciences might not be able to keep pace.

On the other hand the companies are trying their best to accomplish their commercial agenda of rendering the orthodontic management without use of human intervention. We as orthodontists have to be careful accepting the said modality if the profession of orthodontics is to survive. Will then diagnosis and human orthodontic dexterity performing orthodontic management survive. We as Orthodontists will be at mercy of these multinational Conglomerates or our branch remain as the first speciality of Dentistry.

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